

Non-isothermal degradation studies and ion-exchange properties of 4-aminosalicylic acid, urea and formaldehyde copolymer resin

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Abstract : Copolymer resin 4-ASAUF was synthesized by the condensation of 4-aminosalicylic acid (4-ASA) and urea (U) with formaldehyde (F) in the presence of 2 M HCl as catalyst with 2 : 1 : 4 molar ratios of reacting monomers. The structure of the resin was characterized by various spectral techniques like infra-red (FTIR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H and ¹³C NMR) spectroscopy. The empirical formula and empirical weight of the resin were determined by elemental analysis. The morphological feature of the 4-ASAUF copolymer resin was established by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Thermal study of the resin was carried out to determine its mode of decomposition and relative thermal stability. The Freeman-Carroll, Sharp-Wentworth, Friedman and Change methods have been used in the present investigation to calculate thermal activation energy (E_a), order of reaction (n) and frequency factor (z). The chelating ion-exchange property of this copolymer was studied for eight metal ions viz. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions by using batch equilibrium method. The chelating ion-exchange study was carried out over a wide pH range at different time intervals using different electrolyte of various ionic strengths.

Keywords : Copolymer, thermogravimetry, ion-exchange, activation energy.

Introduction

Literature survey reveals that copolymer derived from aromatic compound having substituent like -OH, -COOH, -NH₂ with urea and formaldehyde shows improved ion-exchange capacity, thermal resistance and coordinating properties¹⁻⁴. Ion-exchange process is a powerful and eco-friendly extraction technique for the separation of metal ions and recovery of toxic heavy metal ions from the industrial wastes, tannery effluents and sewages etc.^{5,6}. The chemically modified silica gel *N*-(1-carboxy-6 hydroxy)benzylidene propylamine was used as an ion-exchanger for the removal and pre concentration of hazardous metal ion such as : Cr, Mn, Cd, Pb etc. in natural water samples using batch equilibrium method and Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) technique⁷. Poly (HPMA-co-IA) and poly (HPMA-co-CA) copolymer gel metal absorption increases with pH. The study proved that poly (HPMA-co-IA) and poly (HPMA-co-CA) could be used as metal absorbents for Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions⁸. The chelation

ion-exchange properties of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone-biuret-formaldehyde terpolymers⁹ and resin prepared from 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, oxamide and formaldehyde¹⁰ were investigated by Rahangdale and Tarase respectively. The chelation ion-exchange properties of copolymer resin derived from 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonic acid, oxamide, and formaldehyde indicated that the copolymer had greater selectivity for Fe^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions than for Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions¹¹. The metal ion-binding properties of a copolymer resin derived from *o*-aminophenol, melamine, and formaldehyde has been reported for the metal ions Fe^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}¹². Gurnule *et al.*¹³ reported that a copolymer prepared from salicylic acid, melamine, and formaldehyde was more selective for Fe^{III}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions than for Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions.

Thermal stability is one of the properties that can determine processing and application of materials. The practical use of polymeric material requires knowledge of

thermal resistance power corresponding to certain end point criterion and the operating temperature. Zhao Hong *et al.* studied the thermal decomposition behaviour of phosphorous containing copolymer¹⁴. Polymer has been very useful applications as adhesive, high temperature flame resistance fibres, coating material, semiconductor, catalyst¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Varieties of researches regarding the thermal studies of polymer are emerging out to investigate their renewed application for the betterment of mankind. Area of polymer reaction kinetics is enhanced by applying various models fitting kinetic equation in order to study its kinetic and thermodynamic aspects¹⁸⁻²⁰. Thermal degradation of ethylene propylene diene terpolymer and thermal studies of self-crosslinked terpolymer studied by Naruse *et al.* and Chauhan respectively^{21,22}.

Experimental

Starting materials :

4-Aminosalicylic acid is of analytical grade purity which is purchased from Acros Chemicals, Belgium. Urea and formaldehyde (37%) was purchased from S. D. Fine Chemicals, and metal nitrates, indicators and disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) perches from S. D. Fine Chemicals India. All the solvents like *N,N*-dimethylformamide, dimethyl sulphoxide, tetrahydrofuran, acetone, diethyl ether were procured from Merck, India. Double distilled water was used for all the experiments.

Synthesis :

4-ASAUF copolymer was prepared by condensing 4-aminosalicylic acid (0.2 mol) and urea (0.1 mol) with formaldehyde (0.4 mol) in presence of 2 M HCl as a catalyst in the molar proportion of 2 : 1 : 4 at 120 °C in an oil bath for 5 h. The dark reddish brown resinous solid product was immediately removed, filtered and repeatedly washed with cold-distilled water, dried in air and powdered with the help of mortar and pestle. The product obtained was extracted with diethyl ether to remove excess of 4-aminosalicylic acid-formaldehyde copolymer which might be present along with 4-ASAUF copolymer. Dried resin sample was dissolved in 8% NaOH and regenerated using 1 : 1 HCl/water (v/v) with constant stirring and filtered. This process was repeated twice.

Resulting copolymer sample was washed with boiling water and dried in a vacuum at room temperature. Purified copolymer resin was finely ground to pass through 300-mesh size sieve and kept in a vacuum over silica gel²⁰. The purity of newly synthesized and purified copolymer resin sample has been tested and confirmed by thin layer chromatography technique. Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) was used as a solvent for developing chromatogram and was allowed to run for about 20 min, when the chromatogram was exposed to iodine chamber then we get single colour spot for resin sample. This indicates that the synthesized and purified polymer resin sample has no impurities and used for further studies only after the confirmation of 100% purity of the sample. The chemical reaction of above synthesis is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Chemical reaction of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

Spectral and thermal studies :

Copolymers were subject to elemental analysis for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on Perkin-Elmer 2400 Elemental Analyzer. Infrared spectra were recorded in Frontier transform Infrared spectrophotometer in the range of 4000–500 cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR studies were performed in DMSO-*d*₆ solvent on Bruker Advance-II 400 MHz and ¹³C NMR spectrum was also recorded using Bruker 100 MHz. The non-isothermal thermogravimetric analysis carried out using Perkin-Elmer, Pyris1 Thermogravimetric Analyzer, in air atmosphere with a heating rate 10 °C min^{-1} in the temperature range 50–710 °C.

Ion-exchange property :

The ion-exchange property of the 4-ASAUF copolymer resin was studied by using batch equilibrium method for various metal ion viz. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II},

Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} under three different experimental conditions^{4,23}.

(i) *Determination of metal uptake in the presence of four different electrolytes and their different concentrations :*

Copolymer sample (25 mg) was placed in cleaned glass bottles and each of the electrolytes (25 ml) NaCl, NaNO₃, NaClO₄ and Na₂SO₄ at different concentrations, viz. 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5 and 1 *M*, was added into the bottles. The suspensions were adjusted to pH 2.5 for Fe^{III}, pH 4.5 for Cu^{II} and Hg^{II}, pH 5.0 for Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} and pH 6 for Pb^{II} by adding either 0.1 *M* HCl or 0.1 *M* NaOH. The suspensions were mechanically stirred for 24 h at room temperature. After 24 h, 0.1 *M* of the chosen metal ion solution (2 ml) was added to each bottle and these were again vigorously stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The copolymer was then isolated by filtration and washed with distilled water. The filtrate and the washings were collected and the amount of metal ion was estimated by titrating against standard disodium EDTA solution using an appropriate indicator. A blank experiment was also performed by following the same procedure without the copolymer sample. The amount of metal ions taken up by the copolymer in the presence of a given electrolyte can be calculated from the difference between the actual titration reading and that of the blank reading.

(ii) *Estimation of rate of metal ion uptake as a function of time :*

In order to estimate the time require to reach the state of equilibrium under the given experimental conditions, a series of experiments of the type described above were carried out, in which the metal ion taken up by the chelating resins was determined from time to time at room temperature (in the presence of 25 ml of 1 *M* NaNO₃ solution). It was assumed that, under the given conditions, the state of equilibrium was established within 24 h. The rate of metal uptake is expressed as percentage of the amount of metal ions taken up after a certain time related to that at the state of equilibrium and it can be defined by the following relationship. The percentage amount of metal ions taken up at different time is defined as,

Percentage of metal ion taken up at equilibrium

$$= \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion adsorbed}}{\text{Amount of metal ion adsorbed at equilibrium}} \times 100$$

Percentage of metal ion adsorbed after 1 h

$$= (100X)/Y$$

where, 'X' mg of metal ion adsorbed after 1 h and 'Y' mg of metal ion is adsorbed after 24 h, then by using this expression, the amount of metal adsorbed by copolymer after specific time intervals was calculated and expressed in terms of percentage metal ion adsorbed. This experiment was performed using 0.1 *M* metal nitrate solution of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}.

(iii) *Evaluation of the distribution of metal ions at different pH :*

The distribution of each one of the eight metal ions i.e. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} between the polymer phase and the aqueous phase was determined at room temperature and in the presence of 1 *M* NaNO₃ solution. The experiments were carried out as described above at different pH values. The distribution ratio, *D* is defined by the following relationship.

$$D = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion on resin}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution}} \times \frac{\text{Volume of solution (ml)}}{\text{Weight of resin (g)}}$$

Metal ion adsorbed (uptake) by the resin

$$= \left(\frac{ZX}{Y} \right) \frac{2}{0.025}$$

where, 'Z' is the difference between actual experiment reading and blank reading, 'X' gram is the amount of metal ion in 2 ml 0.1 *M* metal nitrate solution before uptake and 'Y' gram of metal ion in 2 ml of metal nitrate solution after uptake.

Results and discussion

Spectral studies of 4-ASAUF copolymer :

Elemental analysis :

Composition of copolymer obtained on the basis of

elemental analysis data and was found to be in good correlation to that of calculated values the yield of resin was found to be 82% as given in Table 1.

-COOH present in the aromatic ring and involves intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the -NH of Ar-NH₂²⁶. This band seems to be merged with the band arising from

Table 1. Elemental analysis data of 4-ASAUF copolymer

Copolymer	Monomer empirical formula	Empirical formula weight	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					
			C	H	N			
4-ASAUF	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₇	416.38	54.42	54.81	4.68	4.84	13.13	13.46

FT-IR spectra :

The FTIR-spectrum of 4-ASAUF copolymer is represented in Fig. 2 and the data is reported in Table 2. Broad band appeared at 3351.0 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the stretching vibration of the phenolic -OH

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

Table 2. IR frequencies of 4-ASAUF copolymer

Observed band frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	Vibrational mode	Expected band frequencies (cm ⁻¹)
3351.0 b, st	-OH (phenolic)	3200–3400
3001.2 st, w	-NH- (amino)	> 3000
2833.4–2951.0 m, st	-CH ₂ - stretching methylene bridge	2800–2950
1444.6–1587.4 m	>C=C< in aromatics	1400–1600
1269.1 st	Carboxylic acid -COOH	1250–1300
1587.4 st	Ar-NH ₂ (amine)	1560–1640
1209.37 sh, m	C-O str. in phenol	1200
800.0 sh, w	Pentastituted benzene ring	800–950
850.4 sh, w		

groups exhibiting intermolecular hydrogen bonding^{24,25}. The presence of a weak peak at 3001.2 cm⁻¹ describes the -NH- in urea moiety which might be present in copolymeric chain²⁵. The broad band appearing in the spectrum at 3480.1 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the hydroxyl group of

-NH stretching vibrations of the Ar-NH₂ group and this is further confirmed by the -NH bending vibrations appearing at 1587.4 cm⁻¹²⁷. A sharp and weak peak obtained at 2891.3 cm⁻¹, indicates the presence of stretching vibrations of methylene group (-CH₂-) in the copolymer chain^{25,28}. A medium band, displayed between 1444.6–1587.4 cm⁻¹, may be due to stretching vibration of >C=C< in aromatics. Broad and strong bands displayed at 1269.16 cm⁻¹ for confirm the presence of >C=O stretching vibration of carboxylic acid group in the polymer chain²⁵. >C=O stretch in phenol is represented at 1209.3 cm⁻¹. The presence of pentastituted of aromatic ring²⁵ is recognized from the weak band appearing at 800–850 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectral data is given in Table 3 and spectrum is presented in Fig. 3. Spectra reveal different patterns of peaks, since each of them possesses a set of protons having different proton environment. A significant downfield in chemical shift of proton of phenolic -OH group, observed at δ 3.75 ppm, is due to intermediate proton exchange reaction of phenolic -OH group^{29–31}. A weak singlet is observed at δ 7.88 ppm and is due to

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data of 4-ASAUF copolymer

Nature of protons assigned	Expected chemical shift (δ) ppm	Observed chemical shift (δ) ppm of copolymer
1H, phenolic -OH (s)	3.5–9	3.75
1H, Ar-H (s)	6.5–9	7.88
2H, Ar-NH ₂ (s)	3.2–6	3.45
1H, Ar-COOH (s)	10–13	10.3
1H, CH ₂ -NH-C=O (s)	5–8	7.1 and 7.3
2H, Ar-CH ₂ -NH in urea moiety (s)	2.5–3.5	2.53
2H, Ar-CH ₂ (s)	1.5–2.5	2.14

(s) Stand for singlet.

Fig. 3. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

ortho protons of phenol. In urea moiety, the singlet observed in the region δ 7.1 and 7.3 is due to $\text{CH}_2\text{-NH-C=O}$ and singlet observed in the region δ 2.53 ppm due to methylene proton of $\text{Ar-CH}_2\text{-NH}$. A broad singlet observed at δ 3.43 ppm may be assigned to proton of Ar-NH_2 . Singlet observed at δ 2.14 ppm and δ 10.3 ppm due to the proton of Ar-CH_2 and Ar-COOH respectively^{25,29}.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-ASAUF copolymer is shown in Fig. 4 and observed chemical shift assigned on the basis of the literature^{24,29}. The C_1 to C_6 of the first aromatic ring shows the peaks at 160.1, 113.3, 131.1,

Fig. 4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

117.7, 138.4 and 153.3 ppm respectively and the peaks appeared at 39.7 ppm is assigned to the methylene carbon of $\text{Ar-CH}_2\text{-NH}$ linkage²³. The peaks appeared at 173.3 ppm is due to the carbon of the carboxylic acid group and at 160.1, 153.3, 138.4, 117.7, 131.1 and 113.3 ppm with respect to C_1 to C_6 of second aromatic ring of copolymer resins³².

SEM analysis :

The typical microphotograph at 2,000 magnification from SEM of 4-ASAUF is shown in Fig. 5. The SEM

image shows the surface future of the sample. The image of the 4-ASAUF is clearly indicative of a loosely close packed structure with high porosity or voids. The voids

Fig. 5. SEM image of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

presents in the copolymer ligands may be responsible for the swelling behavior and reactivity of active sites buried in the polymer matrix. The image also showed a transitions state between the amorphous and crystalline states. However, more predominantly the copolymer is amorphous, because of the polycondensation reaction³³.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Thermogravimetric analysis is found to be very useful method to determine the thermal stability of copolymer resin. Thermal degradation behavior and kinetic data of copolymer is recorded in Table 4 and thermogram is shown in Fig. 6. The resin 4-ASAUF exhibit three stages of decomposition with initial loss of water molecule. When temperature was raised from 40 to 107 °C, it showed the weight loss about 11.87% and is corresponding to the moisture entrapped in molecule or water of crystallization associated with this copolymer³⁴. This is in agree-

Fig. 6. Decomposition pattern of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

ment with the weight loss calculated theoretically which is about 11.48%. First step is slow decomposition in temperature range 107–231 °C, corresponding to 18.92% mass loss which may be attributed to loss of two hydroxyl group against calculated value of 19.33% loss present per repeat unit of copolymer. The second step of decomposition starts from temperature 231 to 308 °C, corresponding to 51.48% loss which may be attributed to the two -COOH, two -NH₂ and two -CH₂ groups against calculated weight loss of 50.63%. The third step of decomposition start from 308 to 710 °C, corresponding to 99.66% loss which may be attributed to complete remaining moiety having two benzene ring, two -NH, two -CH₂ and one -CO groups against calculated weight loss of 100%.

Thermogram expresses the dependence of change in mass on the temperature which gives information about sample composition, product formed after heating and kinetic parameters. Kinetics parameters have been determined using Friedman^{35,36}, Chang³⁷, Sharp-Wentworth³⁸, and Freeman-Carroll³⁹ methods as follows :

In the present investigation Friedman, Chang, Sharp-Wentworth and Freeman-Carroll methods have been used to determine the kinetic parameters of 4-ASAUF copolymer. The kinetic parameters have been calculated by following four methods.

Friedman method :

$$\ln \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) = \ln(z) + n \ln(1-\alpha) - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (1)$$

where, α is the conversion at time t ; R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol/K) and T is the absolute temperature (K). From the slope of the linear plot of $\ln(1-\alpha)$ vs $1/T$, n can be obtained. The plot of $\ln(d\alpha/dt)$ vs $1/T$ should be linear with the slope E_a/R , from which E_a can be obtained Fig. 7.

Chang method :

$$\ln \left(\frac{\frac{d\alpha}{dt}}{(1-\alpha)^n} \right) = \ln(z) - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 7 has shown Chang method (2) gives plots between $[\ln(d\alpha/dt)/(1-\alpha)^n]$ vs $(1/T)$ which is used to calculate E_a and $\ln(z)$ of respective degradation reaction for best fit-

Fig. 7. Activation energy plot of 4-ASAUF copolymer.

ted value of n (from Friedman equation), which corresponds to correct reaction order for thermal decomposition.

Sharp-Wentworth method :

$$\log \frac{dc/dt}{1-c} = \log \left(\frac{A}{\beta} \right) - \frac{E_a}{2.303 R} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \quad (3)$$

where, dc/dt = rate of change of fraction of weight with change in temperature; β is linear heating rate, dT/dt ; c is the fraction of polymer decomposed at time t . Thus, a

linear plot of $\log \frac{dc/dt}{1-c}$ versus $1/T$ is obtained whose slope gives the value of E_a and A may be evaluated from the intercept (Fig. 7). The linear relationship confirmed that the assumed order is correct.

Freeman and Carroll method :

$$\frac{\Delta \log(dw/dt)}{\Delta \log Wr} = \left(-\frac{E_a}{2.303 R} \right) \cdot \frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \log Wr} + n \quad (4)$$

where, dw/dt = rate of change of weight with time. $Wr = Wc - W$; Wc = weight loss at the completion of reaction; W = total weight loss upto time. E_a = energy of activation; n = order of reaction.

The $\Delta \log(dw/dt)$ and $\Delta \log Wr$ values are taken at regular intervals of $1/T$. In this case $\frac{\Delta \log(dw/dt)}{\Delta \log Wr}$ vs $\frac{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\Delta \log Wr}$ gives a straight line. The slope and intercept are equal to $-(E_a/R)$ and n , respectively (Fig. 7).

A plot of percentage mass loss vs temperature is shown

Table 4. Thermal degradation behavior of 4-ASAUF copolymer

Decomposition steps	Temp. range (°C)	Wt. Loss (%)		Species degraded
		Found	Calcd.	
I	107–231	19.33	18.72	Two (-OH)
II	231–308	51.48	50.63	Two (-COOH), two (-NH ₂) and two (-CH ₂) groups
III	308–710	99.66	100	Two benzene rings with two (-NH), two (-CH ₂) and one (>CO)

Table 5. Thermoanalytical data for degradation of 4-ASAUF copolymer

Kinetic parameter	Kinetic models			
	Friedman	Chang	Sharp-Wentworth	Freeman-Carroll
Activation energy (E_a)	34.72	34.89	12.28	12.44
Order of reaction (n)	2.5	2.5	1	2.2
Frequency factor $\ln(z)$	9.47	3.32	5.12	7.54

in Fig. 6 for a representative 4-ASAUF copolymer. From the TG curves, the thermoanalytical data in Table 5 and decomposition temperature has been determined for different stages as given in Table 4. This kinetic analysis should be a starting point to obtain the useful information on the behavior of samples. Fairly comparable results in the kinetic parameters i.e. E_a , n and $\ln(z)$ are obtained by Friedman and Chang may be due to analogy in mathematical model. Also fairly similar results with slight variations obtained by Sharp-Wentworth and Freeman-Carroll methods.

From the above discussion, it is therefore concluded that for each technique, the values of kinetic parameters depend on calculation methods used. Total calculations obtained from different kinetic models demonstrated that the numerical value of kinetic parameters depends on the mathematical model used to analyze the experimental data and level of degradation⁴⁰. Due to complex phenomena of copolymer degradation process in non-isothermal thermogravimetry, the computed kinetic parameters are in fact only parameters of given mathematical equation which has the form of kinetic rate equation and which is used to fit the weight loss curves accompanying the thermal degradation of polymers in non-isothermal conditions. Low values of frequency factor revealed that decomposition reaction of copolymer may be slow and no other possible reason can be given^{41,42}. As a consequence these kinetic parameters are active from the point of view

of chemical kinetics.

Ion-exchange properties :

Batch equilibrium method developed by De Geiso *et al.*⁴³ and Gregor *et al.*⁴⁴. This technique was used to

Table 6. Evaluation of the effect of different electrolytes and their concentrations on the uptake of 4-ASAUF copolymer resins

Metal ion	Electrolyte (mol/L)	pH	Weight of metal uptake (mmol g ⁻¹) in the presence of			
			NaNO ₂	Na ₂ SO ₄	NaCl	NaClO ₄
			Fe ³⁺	0.01	2.5	1.17
	0.05		1.80	1.66	1.79	1.26
	0.10		2.31	1.34	2.25	1.54
	0.50		2.91	1.10	2.80	1.81
	1.00		3.44	0.45	3.43	2.25
Cu ²⁺	0.01	4.5	1.11	2.87	1.35	0.87
	0.05		1.32	2.26	1.86	1.26
	0.10		1.68	1.83	2.27	1.63
	0.50		2.12	1.39	2.77	1.89
	1.00		2.84	0.89	3.11	2.19
Hg ²⁺	0.01	4.5	0.84	1.73	1.11	0.73
	0.05		1.34	1.17	1.78	1.17
	0.10		1.74	1.02	2.45	1.42
	0.50		2.10	0.79	2.82	1.89
	1.00		2.45	0.25	3.13	2.25
Cd ²⁺	0.01	5.0	0.29	1.77	1.15	0.77
	0.05		0.86	1.39	1.34	0.99
	0.10		1.24	1.09	1.65	1.29
	0.50		1.69	0.79	1.98	1.49
	1.00		1.88	0.49	2.15	1.79
Co ²⁺	0.01	5.0	1.25	1.87	0.82	0.87
	0.05		1.54	1.20	1.12	1.20
	0.10		1.83	0.97	1.34	1.57
	0.50		2.14	0.82	1.69	1.92
	1.00		2.51	0.61	1.93	2.11
Zn ²⁺	0.01	5.0	0.45	1.63	0.97	0.63
	0.05		0.92	1.28	1.15	0.88
	0.10		1.31	1.12	1.70	1.32
	0.50		1.69	0.87	1.92	1.77
	1.00		2.22	0.58	2.46	1.88
Ni ²⁺	0.01	5.0	1.36	2.33	1.12	1.33
	0.05		1.62	2.52	1.86	1.52
	0.10		1.98	2.27	2.11	1.87
	0.50		2.38	1.65	2.28	2.25
	1.00		2.76	1.23	2.65	2.43
Pb ²⁺	0.01	6.0	0.36	1.40	0.83	0.40
	0.05		0.66	1.11	0.92	0.71
	0.10		0.97	0.78	1.26	0.98
	0.50		1.12	0.47	1.45	1.17
	1.00		1.28	0.33	1.68	1.43

Table 7. Comparison of the rates of metal (M) ions^a uptake by 4-ASAUF copolymer resin

Metal ion	pH	Percentage of metal ion uptake ^b at different times (h)						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Fe ³⁺	2.5	49	73.5	98	-	-	-	-
Cu ²⁺	4.5	8	29	48.5	59.5	92	-	-
Hg ²⁺	4.5	14	27.5	43	58	84	-	-
Cd ²⁺	5	11	18.5	32.5	54	73	94	-
Co ²⁺	5	12	29.5	45.5	68	84	-	-
Zn ²⁺	5	3.5	24	38.5	58	69	-	-
Ni ²⁺	5	0	18.5	37.5	67.5	87	-	-
Pb ²⁺	6	5.5	16	34.5	69	70.5	87	-

^a[M(NO₃)₂] = 0.1 mol/L; volume = 2 ml; NaNO₃ = 1.0 mol/L; volume = 25 ml, room temperature.

^bMetal ion uptake = (Amount of metal ion absorbed × 100)/amount of metal ion absorbed at equilibrium.

ride (Cl⁻), chlorate (ClO₄⁻) and sulfate (SO₄²⁻) at various concentrations on the equilibrium of metal-resin interaction. The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of the various electrolytes with different concentrations on the amount of the metal ions taken up by copolymer sample which might be used in the purification of waste solution. The results are presented in Table 6 and chelate formation by the 4-ASAUF copolymer is shown in Fig. 8. This reveals that the amount of metal ions taken up by a given amount of copolymer depends on the nature and concentration of the electrolyte present in the solution. Generally as concentration of the electrolyte increases, the ionization decreases, number of ligands (negative ions of electrolyte) decrease in the solution which forms the complex with less number of metal ions and therefore more number of ions may available for adsorption on copoly-

Table 8. Distribution ratio *D*^a of various metal ions^b as function of the pH by 4-ASAUF copolymer resin

Metal ion	pH	Distribution ratio of metal ion at different pH								
		1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	5	6	6.5
Fe ³⁺	2.5	60.14	94.81	178.55	391.11	-	-	-	-	-
Cu ²⁺	4.5	-	-	38.62	42.76	47.29	81.68	144.19	613.33	1013.32
Hg ²⁺	4.5	-	-	27.47	69.27	81.68	290.75	341.72	391.11	539.25
Cd ²⁺	5	-	-	137.14	164.35	206.32	260.39	327.61	431.51	613.33
Co ²⁺	5	-	-	20.22	27.47	52.27	70.69	113.33	237.03	314.48
Zn ²⁺	5	-	-	17.30	34.82	41.90	70.69	118.70	200.63	290.75
Ni ²⁺	5	-	-	0.53	15.93	49.23	103.52	260.39	539.25	1013.3
Pb ²⁺	6	-	-	11.70	17.30	23.96	31.32	51.24	118.70	227.36

^a*D* = Weight (in mg) of metal ions taken up by 1 g of copolymer/weight (in mg) of metal ions present in 1 ml of solution.

^b[M(NO₃)₂] = 0.1 mol/L; volume = 2 ml; NaNO₃ = 1.0 mol/L; volume = 25 ml, time 24 h (equilibrium state) at room temperature.

study ion-exchange properties of 4-ASAUF copolymer resin and results are presented in Tables 6–8. Eight metal ions Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in the form of aqueous metal nitrate solution were used. The ion-exchange study was carried out using three experimental variables such as (a) electrolyte and its ionic strength, (b) uptake time and (c) pH of the aqueous medium. Among these three variables, two were kept constant and only one was varied at a time to evaluate its effect on metal uptake of the polymer similar to the earlier co-workers^{4,23}.

(i) *Determination of metal uptake in the presence of four different electrolytes and their different concentrations :*

We examined the influence of nitrate (NO₃⁻), chlo-

Fig. 8. Chelate structure of the 4-ASAUF copolymer resin.

mer. Hence on increasing concentration, uptake of metal ions may be increased, which is the normal trend. But the trend is different in different electrolytes and their different concentrations due to the formation of more or less stable complex of electrolyte ligand or copolymer with metal ions.

If electrolyte ligand-metal ion complex is weaker than polymer metal ion chelates, the more number of metal ions can form complex with polymer hence uptake of metal ion is more. But if this complex is stronger than polymer metal ion chelates, more number of metal ions form strong complex with electrolyte ligand which make metal uptake capacity lower by polymer.

In the presence of nitrate (NO_3^-), chloride (Cl^-), chlorate (ClO_4^-), the uptake of Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions increases with increasing concentration of the electrolyte, whereas in the presence of sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) ions the amount of the above mentioned ions taken up by the copolymer decreases with increasing concentration of the electrolyte²³.

The ratio of physical core structure of the resin is significant in the uptake of different metal ions by the resin copolymer. The rate of metal ion uptake for NO_3^- , Cl^- , ClO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} electrolytes at various concentrations follows the order as : $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Hg}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$. The amount of metal ion uptake by the 4-ASAUF copolymer resin is found to be higher when comparing to the other tercopolymer resins^{2,4,13,45}. The uptake of metal ions by the copolymer resin was calculated by use of the formula and expressed in mmol g^{-1} .

Metal ion adsorbed (uptake) by resin

$$= (X - Y) Z \text{ mmol/g}^{-1}$$

where, 'Z' ml is the difference between actual experimental reading and blank reading, 'X' mg is metal ion in the 2 ml 0.1 M metal nitrate solution before uptake and 'Y' mg is metal ion in the 2 ml 0.1 M metal nitrate solution after uptake.

By using this equation the uptake of various metal ions by resin can be calculated and expressed in terms of

millimols per gram of the copolymer. Thus the metal intake of resin was analyzed by mass balance calculation.

(ii) Estimation of rate of metal ion uptake as a function of time :

The rate of metal adsorption was determined to find out the shortest period of time for which equilibrium could be achieved while operating as close to equilibrium conditions as possible. As shaking time increases the copolymer gets more time for adsorption, hence uptake increases (Table 7). It shows the data of dependence of the rate of metal ion uptake on the nature of the metal ions. The rate refers to the change in the concentration of the metal ions in the aqueous solution which is in contact with the given copolymer. The results show that the rate of metal uptake may depend upon the nature of the metal ions and their ionic size. Thus the rate of metal ion uptake follows the order :

Metal ion : $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Hg}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$:

Ionic size : 0:55 0:57 0:69 0:90 0:90 0:90 1:10 1:19

The sequence of rate of metal ion uptake indicates that the rate is directly proportional to the size of the metal ion. For example Fe^{III} has more charge and small size, therefore equilibrium is attained within three hours, while other four transition ions Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} have nearly equal cationic size, having same charges, therefore required 5 h to attain equilibrium, while Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} have large atomic size, therefore requiring 6 h to attain equilibrium. The trend is in good agreement with earlier workers^{4,23,46,47}.

(iii) Evaluation of the distribution of metal ions at different pH :

The effect of pH on the metal binding capacity of the synthesized copolymers shows that relative amount of metal ion adsorbed by the copolymer resin increase with increasing pH of the medium (Table 8). The study was carried from pH 1.5 to 6.5 to prevent absorption or hydrolysis or precipitation of the metal ions at higher pH. The data on the distribution ratio as a function of pH indicates that the distribution of each metal between the polymer phase and aqueous phase increase with increasing pH of the medium. The magnitude of increase, however, is different for different metal ions.

It is observed that Fe^{III} ion has highest working pH is

3 because above this pH Fe^{III} found to be absorb in the resin and it has lower distribution ratio, since Fe^{III} forms complex with electrolyte, which shows crowding effect. This steric hindrance may be lower the distribution ratio of Fe^{III} ion. Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} have higher distribution ratio over pH range of 2.5 to 6.5 which may be due to the less steric hindrance. Thus the value of distribution ratio for given pH depends upon the nature and stability of chelate formation for particular metal ion^{4,23,47}. In case of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} purely electrostatic factors are responsible, the ion uptake capacity of Cd^{II} is lower owing to the large size of its hydrated ion than that of Cu^{II}. The steric influence of the amine group and hydroxyl group in 4-ASAUF resin is probably responsible for their observed low binding capacities for various metal ions. The higher value of distribution ratio for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} at pH 2.5 to 6.5 may be due to the formation of most stable complex with chelating ligands. Therefore the copolymer under study has more selectivity of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions in the range of pH 2.5 to 6.5 than other ions which form rather weak complex. While from pH 1.5 to 3 the polymer has more selectivity of Fe^{III} ions. The order of distribution ratio of metal ions measured in pH range 1.5 to 6.5 is found to be Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Hg^{II} > Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Pb^{II} > Cd^{II}^{4,23,47}. The 4-ASAUF copolymer resin is a cation exchange resin and in cation exchange resin the equilibrium may be expressed in terms of mass action law and the relative amount of metal ions in the resin phase and can be determined by the relative concentrations of these ions in the bulk of the solution.

$$K = \frac{[\text{H}^+][(\text{Resin OH}^-) \text{M}^+]}{[(\text{Resin OH}^-) \text{H}^+][\text{M}^+]}$$

Equilibrium constant (K) of this type are useful for comparing the relative affinities for a resin towards various ions. The cations are arranged in an affinity scale according to the numerical value of K . For the metal ions under investigation, the relative affinity is Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} ≈ Ni^{II} > Cd^{II} ≈ Hg^{II} > Co^{II} ≈ Zn^{II} ≈ Pb^{II}. The strength of electrolyte and dielectric constant also affect the metal distribution or accumulation of resin.

Conclusion

Synthesis of targeted copolymer (4-ASAUF) has been confirmed which is supported by the results obtained by

the elemental analysis and spectral data. Thermogram has shown three degradation stages, first indicating degradation of two OH, second shows removal of two -COOH, two -NH₂ and two -CH₂ groups and third step represents two side benzene rings with methylene groups, two (-NH) and one >C=O. Friedman, Chang methods show nearly similar values of kinetic parameters may be due to resemblance in mathematical model whereas results obtained from Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth are in well agreement with each other. The values of kinetic parameters are significantly controlled by level of degradation and calculation methods used to analyze the experimental data. It is observed that the metal complexes taken in the present study are pH dependent and each has a definite pH for optimum chelation, and it is useful property to separate a particular metal ion from a solution of different metal ions using this copolymer. The surface of the copolymer resin was found to be more amorphous, clearly indicating the suitability of the synthesized resin for ion-exchange applications.

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